

FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF THE TERMS CONCEPT, NOTION, CONTENT AND MEANING IN LINGUISTICS

Abdullayeva Shakhnoza

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13677919>

Abstract. This thesis analyzes a series of terms – “concept”, “notion”, “meaning”, which are closely related to each other and constantly interact in modern linguistics. The applicability of this work is apparent, since its matter is characterized by a certain terminological ambiguity. Distinction of these terms is necessary to ascertain their roles in the acquisition, comprehension and expression of knowledge about the real world.

Keywords: Word, Lexical meaning, Concept, notion, English language.

INTRODUCTION

The term “concept” is one of the most complicated ideas in cognitive linguistics; it is quite difficult to be defined. In recent years, the term has been broadly interpreted and regarded as ambiguous in the social sciences and humanities. It was introduced with a certain degree of pathos and sometimes through a cognitive metaphor: it was called “a multi-dimensional cluster of sense”, “a semantic slice of life” [1], “a gene of culture” [3], etc. Today, the term “concept” is widely used in various fields of linguistics. It has entered into the notional system of cognitive, semantic, and cultural linguistics.

MAIN PART

When a concept acquires its linguistic expression, the linguistic means used for this purpose act as means of verbalization, language representation, linguistic objectification of the concept. In language, a concept can be verbalized by existing lexemes, free phrases, phraseological and paremiological units, structural or positional sentence schemes and even whole texts. It is important to bear in mind that a phenomenon name or designation is not equivalent to a concept. Concepts as elements of consciousness are quite independent in the language. According to V. Evans, concepts are intermediaries between the words and extralinguistic reality [3]. Only those phenomena of the reality can become a concept, that are relevant to and valuable for a particular culture, which have a large number of language units for their fixation, are the subject of proverbs and sayings, poetry and prose texts, i.e. they are considered to be the bearers of the national cultural memory.

A scientific notion is objective (it is based on the essence of phenomena comprehended by scientists through hard work after years of learning), and a naive notion is anthropocentric (it is based on practical experience of humans). Every day and scientific notions are sometimes in direct conflict with each other. For example, in everyday speech, anyone would talk about sunrise or sunset, without mentioning the rotation of the Earth around the Sun, about warm clothes, but not about the things that retain heat, etc.

There are two main directions to consider the relations “notion-concept”. The representatives of one tenor tend to equate these terms and to regard them as interchangeable synonyms. This view of the problem is presented in the works of G. Lakoff, V. Postovalova, N. Shvedova, M. Nikitin, A. Babushkin, A. Khudyakov and others who claim that a notion and a concept are close phenomena; “nowadays, linguists hardly use the term “notion”

in its classical sense and prefer to speak of mental structures referred to as “concepts” [3, p. 14].

“Concept” and “notion” are not equal to each other: the first term is much wider in its content than the second term, as the whole is always more voluminous than its part. Such understanding can be traced in the works of P. Abelard, M. Pimenova, I. Sternin, V. Karasik, G. Slyshkin, L. Cherneiko, V. Maslova and others. Thoughts about the relationship of concept and idea as a whole and a part can be found in the works of Pierre Abelard (1079 - 1142), the founder of conceptualism. In his view, the scope of manifestation of concept is more diverse, it includes emotions, intuition, affects, feelings, etc. [3]. While a notion is a thought of a certain object or phenomenon, a concept is an individual sense showing the internal features of an object (they may be not very important): images, symbols, feelings, evaluations – in other words, it is “the idea involving not only abstract, but concrete-associative and emotional-evaluative characteristics” [5].

CONCLUSION

The raised issue of the difference between the terms “concept”, “notion” and “meaning” can have the following conclusions. The problem of these terms differentiation is still one of the most pressing and intractable problems in modern linguistics. Researchers observe both unifying and distinctive characteristics of these words. The author’s opinion is that “lexical meaning”, “notion” and “concept” are different terms. They are interrelated, but not equivalent. It seems reasonable that they belong to similar categories of thinking but are taken in different systems of relationships.

References:

1. Churilina, L. (ed.) (2018). Actual problems of modern linguistics (3rd ed.). Moscow: Flinta Nauka, 416 p.
2. Alefirenko, N.F. (ed.) (2014). Theory of language. Introductory course: a higher school tutorial for students of Philology. Moscow: Publishing Centre “Academy”, 368 p.
3. Babushkin, A.P. (ed.) (2016). Types of concepts in language lexical-phraseological semantics. Voronezh: Publishing house of Voronezh State University, 104 p.
4. Babushkin, A.P. (2019). Translation of realia in the light of cognitive semantics problems. In: Babushkin A.P., & Zhukova M.G. (eds.), Problems of text cultural adaptation, (pp.11-13). Voronezh.
5. Karasik, V.I., Krasavsky, N.A., & Slyshkin G.G. (eds.) (2019). Cultural linguistic conceptology. Volgograd: Paradigma, 115 p.